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Item Type	Other; Avestia Publishing
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DOI	https://doi.org/10.11159/iccste25.351
Publisher	Avestia Publishing
Journal	International Conference on Civil Structural and Transportation Engineering
Rights	info:eu-repo/semantics/openAccess
Download date	21/04/2026 11:27:22
Item License	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Link to Item	http://hdl.handle.net/10757/687656

Damage States and Seismic Performance Levels of a Three-Story Confined Masonry Structure, Lima, Peru

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Abstract - This research addresses the issue of self-construction in the district of Lurigancho-Chosica, using the Asociación Pro Vivienda Paz y Desarrollo San Pedro y San Pablo as a case study. In this area, structural deficiencies are identified due to the use of non-standard materials and the absence of technical design. As a solution, the design of a three-story confined masonry dwelling is proposed, complying with the Peruvian National Building Code (RNE). Field data was collected from 15 representative homes using data collection forms to identify the number of projected floors and typical lot dimensions (240 m²). Based on this, a three-level confined masonry dwelling was designed, applying habitability and structural safety criteria according to standards A.020, E.030, and E.070 of the RNE. The structural design was carried out through a linear static analysis using ETABS software, determining dimensions and reinforcement of main elements. Then, the nonlinear behavior of the structure was evaluated using STERA 3D software, applying a nonlinear time-history dynamic analysis with seismic records scaled to the design spectrum (Standard E.030) using a seismic reduction factor $R = 1$. From the obtained interstory drifts, structural damage levels were classified according to the criteria of Zavala et al. [1], allowing the estimation of the dwelling's seismic vulnerability. Finally, structural plans were developed. The proposed design complies with current regulations and demonstrates good structural performance under severe earthquakes, representing a safe and technically reliable solution to the deficiencies observed in the self-construction context of the study area.

Keywords: Confined masonry, drifts, seismic performance, damage state

1. Introduction

In recent years, a significant increase has been observed in the use of the confined masonry structural system for housing construction in Peru. Between 2007 and 2017, the number of such dwellings increased by 43.7% [2], indicating a marked preference for this construction system. This preference is based on the system's affordability, accessibility, and potential resistance—if construction procedures strictly follow current regulations [3]. However, a large percentage of these dwellings are self-built, making them highly vulnerable to collapse during major seismic events. An example is the 2007 earthquake in southern Peru, in Ica, with a magnitude of 7.9 Mw. This event demonstrated that houses built with handmade bricks and lacking proper design criteria were the most structurally affected. Of the 134,109 damaged homes, 46,555 collapsed [4]. Therefore, seismic-resistant design following the applicable standards is as crucial as proper construction practices and the use of specified materials.

Globally, confined masonry offers a cost-effective and safe structural solution for housing in seismic zones. This is since confinement elements have smaller cross-sections compared to other structural systems, resulting in lower concrete usage and, consequently, economic savings. These confinement elements also provide lateral stability to the masonry walls [5]. Additionally, the masonry units combined with reinforced concrete boundary elements allow for a uniform distribution of loads [6].

Nevertheless, in inland regions of Peru, there is a notable deficit in the proper use of this structural system. Studies have shown the high seismic vulnerability of dwellings where poor construction practices prevail. For instance, in the district of Chupuro, province of Huancayo, Junín region, the seismic vulnerability of 226 confined masonry houses was assessed using the Rapid Visual Screening (RVS) technique. Results showed that 61% of the houses were vulnerable to seismic damage, classified as grade 2 (moderate damage) and grade 3 (severe damage) [7]. A similar situation was found in the district of Huancán, also in Huancayo, where 30 homes were assessed using INDECI's methodology and ETABS software. The analysis revealed that 40% of homes exhibited very high vulnerability, 50% high vulnerability, and the remaining 10% moderate vulnerability [8]. In Miramar, Trujillo province, La Libertad region, a more critical situation was observed. Based on data from 359 homes collected through direct observation, surveys, INDECI methodology, and structural assessments, it was determined that 90% of these houses had high seismic vulnerability.

2. Methodology

The development of this research followed a sequence of procedures, which were divided into four phases:

The first phase began with the preparation of field data collection forms, aiming to record and assess the needs of residents for safe housing in the event of earthquakes. Subsequently, field visits were conducted in the district of Lurigancho, Lima, Peru, to understand the current conditions of the area and define a study zone. The selection criteria included high population density, predominance of confined masonry dwellings, similar lot sizes, poor construction quality, and evident housing needs among the local population, particularly for low-budget housing.

The second phase consisted of the design of the confined masonry dwelling, starting with the architectural layout. The configuration of each space was based on compliance with Standard A.020 and on meeting the needs of residents. A preliminary configuration of the structural elements was also prepared, including masonry walls, tie-columns, beams, and slabs. Using seismic analysis in ETABS software and validating the structural model, the structural elements were designed by determining the required dimensions and quantity of steel reinforcement. Final architectural and structural plans were then developed for the prototype house to serve as a model for the local population.

The third phase involved modeling the structure in STERA 3D software, defining the structural elements, reinforcement quantities, and material properties. Relevant seismic records were selected and scaled to the design spectrum with $R = 1$ to conduct a nonlinear time-history dynamic analysis. This analysis yielded interstory drift values for each level, which served as the main parameter for classifying structural damage.

The fourth phase comprised the presentation of the interstory drift results obtained from the nonlinear time-history analysis, interpreting the dynamic behavior of the model under severe seismic demands. Based on these results, structural damage levels were classified per story using the drift thresholds proposed by Zavala et al. [1]. This classification allowed for a comparative interpretation of seismic behavior and an assessment of structural damage severity under various seismic demands, expressed in qualitative categories such as slight, moderate, severe, or collapse.

3. Current situation

Field visits were conducted in a sector of the district of Lurigancho, located in the city of Lima, Peru, specifically in the area known as “Asociación Pro Vivienda Paz y Desarrollo San Pedro y San Pablo.” A representative sample of 15 confined masonry dwellings was selected. These dwellings were recorded on-site using standardized data collection forms, and the information was processed accordingly. The results indicate that most of the dwellings have a lot area of approximately 240 m² and are single-story constructions, as shown in Figure 1. Additionally, a high level of occupancy per dwelling was observed. This is largely due to the economic limitations of the residents, who cannot afford to build additional floors. Consequently, a clear need was identified for structurally safe and economically feasible housing solutions that would improve the quality of life for the population.

Fig. 1: Number of homes in relation to the number of stories built.

4. Structural Proposal

Based on the analysis of the collected field data, a confined masonry housing design was proposed with seismic-resistant characteristics in compliance with Standard E.030. Figure 2 shows the distribution of walls and room layout for the first floor, which includes two apartments. Each apartment was designed with the following spaces: living room, dining room, kitchen, laundry area, master bedroom

Fig. 2. Proposed housing wall distribution

5. Verification of Structural Walls

The wall density was verified in each direction to ensure proper seismic performance and to avoid excessive torsion deformation, using Equation (1):

$$\frac{\sum L \cdot t}{A_p} \geq \frac{Z \cdot U \cdot S \cdot N}{56} \quad (1)$$

As shown in Table 1, the wall densities in both directions exceed the minimum required values, and the densities in the X and Y directions are similar. This balance contributes to the structural system's ability to avoid localized stress concentrations.

Table 1: Wall Density Check in Both Directions

Direction	Minimum Density	Wall Density	Verification
X Axis	0.025	0.041	Complies
Y Axis	0.025	0.048	Complies

Additionally, vertical load stress verification was conducted using the most representative wall or the one subjected to the highest loads. This criterion simplifies the procedure and allows the analysis to focus on the most critical structural elements, offering insight into the system's overall performance. In this study, the wall experiencing the highest axial force was identified as Wall X7. As shown in Table 2, the acting stress in this wall is below the allowable axial stress, indicating compliance with the applicable code requirements.

Table 2: Vertical Load Verification for the Most Stressed Wall

Most Stressed Wall	f'm (kg/cm ²)	Acting Stress (kg/cm ²)	Axial Stress (Wall Head) (kg/cm ²)	Allowable Axial Stress (kg/cm ²)	Verification
X7	85	10.56	11.75	12.75	COMPLIES

Cracking of the walls was also checked, ensuring that the shear stress caused by a moderate earthquake does not exceed the maximum shear that the load-bearing walls can withstand without entering the inelastic range and initiating cracking [9]. Tables 3 and 4 summarize the verification for the most stressed walls in each principal direction under moderate seismic action.

Table 3: Cracking Verification under Moderate Earthquake – X Direction

Wall	L (m)	t (m)	Pg (ton)	Ve (ton)	Me (ton-m)	alpha	a	Vm (ton)	0.55Vm	Condition
X7	4.75	0.23	17.33	13.34	28.84	2.20	1	48.03	26.41	OK
X5	3.85	0.13	10.26	7.15	12.78	2.15	1	22.53	12.39	OK
X2	2.70	0.13	4.80	4.01	6.25	1.73	1	15.25	8.39	OK

Table 4: Cracking Verification under Moderate Earthquake – Y Direction

MURO	L (m)	t (m)	Pg (ton)	Ve (ton)	Me (ton-m)	alpha	a	Vm (ton)	0.55Vm	Condition
Y5	2.60	0.13	4.54	2.95	4.19	1.83	1	14.67	8.07	OK
Y6	2.60	0.13	4.49	2.94	4.19	1.82	1	14.66	8.06	OK
Y9	3.53	0.13	8.13	4.55	6.96	2.30	1	20.34	11.19	OK

6. Design of Structural Elements

After defining the structural elements, a pinned base condition was considered for the modeling process, given that confined masonry walls do not have a rigid connection with the foundation. This is because the mortar that joins the masonry masonry units to the plinth beam does not provide sufficient stiffness to restrain out-of-plane rotation. Subsequently, the layout of the structural elements—such as masonry walls, tie-columns, beams, and slabs—was developed in ETABS software (see Figure 3), according to the previously defined parameters and based on the structural configuration intended for seismic analysis.

Fig. 3: Modeling in ETABS of the Three-Story Confined Masonry Dwelling

In the design of confinement columns, the internal forces—such as shear, tension, and compression—were first determined in accordance with the provisions of Standard E.070. Based on this, a friction-shear design was carried out, where it was verified that the proposed column sections could withstand the shear forces. Subsequently, the vertical reinforcements were determined using a friction coefficient (μ) of 0.8, a strength reduction factor (ϕ) of 0.85, and the internal forces (shear and tension). After calculating the required steel area, the compression design was performed, confirming that the proposed column sections were adequate to resist the compressive loads. Finally, stirrups were designed for each column, determining that the spacing should be 5 cm. Figure 4 shows the reinforcement detail of each column used in the structural configuration of the dwelling.

COLUMN SCHEDULE			
COLUMNS STORIES	C-1	C-2	C-3
STORY 1 TO STORY 3	<p>4Ø5/8" 1Ø1/4":1@0.05 8@0.05,Rto.@.25 c/ext.</p>	<p>4Ø1/2" 1Ø1/4":1@0.05 7@0.06,Rto.@.25 c/ext.</p>	<p>8Ø1/2" 2Ø1/4":1@0.05 8@0.05,Rto.@.25 c/ext.</p>
	$f_c=210\text{kg/cm}^2$	$f_c=210\text{kg/cm}^2$	$f_c=210\text{kg/cm}^2$

Fig. 4: Reinforcement detail of reinforced concrete confinement ($f_c = 210 \text{ kg/cm}^2$), prepared using AutoCAD software

For the design of beams, calculations were performed to determine both vertical and horizontal reinforcement for bond beams, tie-beams, and lintels. The amount of required steel was calculated according to Standard E.070, which states that the reinforcement must be capable of resisting tensile forces. For vertical tensile reinforcement, a strength reduction factor (ϕ) of 0.9 was applied along with the pure tensile force experienced by each beam, allowing the calculation of the minimum steel area. Regarding stirrup configuration, E.070 suggests a minimum distribution with a 6 mm bar diameter. For this research, a similar configuration was used, but with $\frac{1}{4}$ " diameter stirrups to ensure adequate performance under tensile stresses. Figure 5 presents the reinforcement detail and stirrup layout for each beam type.

BEAM SCHEDULE			
	VA-1	VA-2	
$f_c=210\text{kg/cm}^2$	<p>4Ø1/2" 1Ø1/4":1@0.05 4@0.10,Rto.@.25 c/ext.</p>	<p>4Ø1/2" 1Ø1/4":1@0.05 4@0.10,Rto.@.25 c/ext.</p>	$f_c=210\text{kg/cm}^2$
$f_c=210\text{kg/cm}^2$	<p>4Ø1/2" 1Ø1/4":1@0.05 4@0.10,Rto.@.25 c/ext.</p>	<p>4Ø1/2" 1Ø1/4":1@0.05 4@0.10,Rto.@.25 c/ext.</p>	

Fig. 5. Reinforcement detail of reinforced concrete beams ($f_c = 210 \text{ kg/cm}^2$), prepared using AutoCAD software

For the design of the lightweight slab, a preliminary thickness of $e = 0.20$ m was considered, including a 5 cm upper slab and a joist spacing of 0.40 m. Once the maximum moments were obtained using load combinations in ETABS software, the steel area for design was calculated as specified in Standard E.060 for Reinforced Concrete [10]. The longitudinal reinforcement results for the lightweight slab were as follows: bottom: $1\text{Ø}1\frac{1}{2}''$, top: $2\text{Ø}3\frac{3}{8}''$, with a development length of 1.20 m and hooks using $1\text{Ø}3\frac{3}{8}''$. The reinforcement detail of the lightweight slab is shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Reinforcement detail of lightweight slab, prepared using AutoCAD software

7. Nonlinear Dynamic Analysis

To assess the seismic performance of the three-story confined masonry dwelling, a time-history dynamic analysis was conducted using the software STERA 3D, which enables the modeling of concentrated nonlinear elements in three-dimensional structures, as illustrated in Figure 7. The mechanical properties of the masonry walls were incorporated based on Technical Standard E.070, along with the geometric characteristics and gravity loads for each level.

Fig. 7: Nonlinear Seismic Response Analysis with the 1966 Huacho Ground Motion in STERA 3D

Three representative real earthquake records—Huacho (1966), Ancash (1970), and Pisco (2007)—were selected processed in accordance with Article 4.7 of Standard E.030. Baseline correction and spectral matching were performed the SeismoSignal and SeismoMatch software, adjusting the accelerograms to a target demand spectrum with $R = 1$ and damping.

Subsequently, the processed records were applied to the structural model in STERA 3D, configuring the three seismic components (NS, EW, UD) in alignment with the analysis axes. Interstory drifts were obtained for each floor and ground motion, confirming that they do not exceed the permissible limit of 0.00625, as established by Standard E.030. Figure 8 illustrates the interstory drift response to the 1970 Ancash earthquake, revealing a controlled deformation pattern. Likewise, Table 5 summarizes the maximum drift values in the X and Y directions for the three ground motions analyzed, showing that in all cases the values remain below the code-defined threshold, thereby indicating adequate structural performance of the proposed housing unit.

Fig. 8: Interstory Drifts from Nonlinear Analysis under the 1970 Ancash Earthquake

Table 5: Maximum Interstory Drifts by Direction for the Three Earthquake Records

Earthquake	Maximum Drift X-axis ($\times 10^{-3}$)	Maximum Drift Y-axis ($\times 10^{-3}$)	E.030 Permissible Limit ($\times 10^{-3}$)
Pisco (2007)	0.8716	0.5140	6.25
Ancash (1970)	1.1264	0.7856	6.25
Huacho (1966)	0.9872	1.0408	6.25

8. Results Analysis

To evaluate the seismic performance of the analyzed structure, the damage level per story was classified based on the interstory drifts obtained, considering three representative seismic scenarios: the 1970 Ancash, 2007 Pisco, and 1966 Huacho earthquakes. For this purpose, the drift thresholds proposed by Zavala et al. [1] in their study “Development of Fragility Function for Typologies of Confined Masonry Dwellings in Metropolitan Lima and Callao Cities” were used as a reference. This study establishes interstory drift ranges associated with different structural damage levels for confined masonry buildings constructed with handmade bricks and industrial hollow bricks, as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Classification of Damage States and Seismic Performance Levels Proposed by Zavala et al. [1]

Drift ($\times 10^{-3}$) ML1	Drift ($\times 10^{-3}$) ML2	Damage State	Performance Level
$\gamma < 0.48$	$\gamma < 0.47$	No Damage	Operational (O)
$0.48 \leq \gamma < 1.25$	$0.47 \leq \gamma < 0.67$	Slight	Immediate Occupancy (IO)
$1.25 \leq \gamma < 2.86$	$0.67 \leq \gamma < 1.00$	Moderate	Life Safety (LS)
$2.86 \leq \gamma < 4.00$	$1.00 \leq \gamma < 1.82$	Severe	Collapse Prevention (CP)
$\gamma \geq 8.00$	$\gamma \geq 5.00$	Collapse	Collapse (C)

Note: Adapted from [1]

Although the present case study involves a confined masonry building constructed with industrial solid bricks, it is considered that both systems share a similar structural typology—characterized by load-bearing masonry walls confined with reinforced concrete elements—which allows for a comparative reference of seismic performance. It is important to note that, despite differences in the mechanical properties of the various brick types (such as compressive strength and stiffness), the adopted methodology is justified by the compatibility of the construction system and the lack of specific fragility curves for structures built with industrial hollow bricks. Accordingly, Table 7 presents the story drift values induced by the seismic record that generated the highest structural response (Ancash 1970), along with their corresponding damage level classification according to the defined thresholds.

Table 7: Damage Levels and Interstory Drifts – 1970 Ancash Earthquake

Story	Drift X ($\times 10^{-3}$)	Damage State	Drift Y ($\times 10^{-3}$)	Damage State
3°	0.4748	No Damage	0.3332	No Damage
2°	0.8624	Slight	0.6108	Slight
1°	1.1264	Slight	0.7856	Slight

For the seismic scenario described, the damage state was identified as slight, corresponding to the Immediate Occupancy (IO) performance level, in accordance with the criteria established by Zavala et al. [1]. This finding demonstrates that the proposed structural configuration is reliable and exhibits adequate seismic performance, even under severe ground motions.

Consequently, it can be affirmed that the analyzed structural system, consisting of confined masonry walls, is technically sound and suitable for implementation in regions of high seismic hazard such as the study area.

9. Conclusion

The seismic analysis of a proposed three-story confined masonry housing unit validated the effectiveness of the structural system under severe seismic demands, complying with the permissible limits established by Standard E.030 of the Peruvian National Building Code. It was verified that the wall density in both principal directions exceeds the minimum required thresholds, ensuring balanced structural behavior and minimizing torsional response.

Axial force assessments and crack verification analyses confirmed that the walls adequately withstand vertical loads and moderate seismic actions. The interstory drifts obtained from the nonlinear dynamic analysis—based on three representative ground motion records—remained below the code-prescribed limits in all cases, demonstrating adequate stiffness and energy dissipation capacity.

In terms of damage state, the structure predominantly exhibited a slight damage pattern, even under the most demanding scenario (Ancash earthquake, 1970), corresponding to the Immediate Occupancy (IO) performance level. This outcome is particularly significant in high seismic vulnerability contexts such as Lima, where informal housing construction is prevalent.

Therefore, it is concluded that the proposed design represents a technically sound and feasible solution to mitigate the adverse effects of informal housing practices, offering a replicable and efficient alternative for residential construction in urban expansion areas exposed to high seismic hazard.

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